

PLAN'EAT

Data Management Plan

Deliverable D7.1

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DELIVERABLE PLAN'EAT – D7.1

Data Management Plan

PLAN'EAT

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Nature of the deliverable

R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	X
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.	

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified, EU RESTRICTED, CONFIDENTIAL or SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

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Project abstract

The EU food system is under considerable pressure for change due to its negative climate, environmental and health impacts. Food system transition will require changing dietary habits of millions of Europeans. PLAN'EAT aims at advancing the scientific basis on factors influencing dietary behaviour and the health, environmental and socio-economic impacts of dietary patterns, and deliver solutions for transition through a transdisciplinary and multi-level approach.

PLAN'EAT will co-create data and interventions in a pan-EU network of 9 Living Labs and a Policy Lab. These living labs will focus on a broad range of population groups, varying according to age, culture, health and socio-economic status. PLAN'EAT entails four steps that feed into each other:

- (1) A snapshot of European dietary patterns and food environments will be provided by respectively basing on existing data from 11 EU countries and by involving local population groups in LLs.
- (2) Factors and drivers influencing dietary behaviour at macro- (food system), meso- (food environment) and micro- (individual) levels will be deeply investigated.
- (3) A True Cost Accounting database and methodology will be developed and applied, for the first time, on dietary patterns, providing integrated insights into the diverse impacts of current and future diets, including possible synergies and trade-offs.
- (4) A solution package will be co-developed with food chain actors, consumers and policymakers, including:
 - a Food System Dashboard, setting out context-specific food policy recommendations;
 - interventions targeting Farm to Fork actors, supporting farmers, food industries, retailers and food services to create suitable food environments;
 - personalised advisory tools to empower consumers; and
 - improved dietary advice and communication strategies to target populations at large.

PLAN'EAT will enable >58500 European consumers to shift to healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns by 2032, reducing premature mortality by 20% and greenhouse gas emissions from local food supply chains by 23% in 39 EU areas.

Glossary

Table 1: Glossary

Terms	Definition
Anonymisation	The data has been rendered anonymous in such a way that the data can no longer be identified and excludes any possibility to identify the data subject. Therefore, anonymised data is no longer personal data and thus outside the scope of data protection law.
Data	Information, especially facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered and used to help decision-making, or information in an electronic form that can be stored and used by a computer
Data Protection Officer	The person designed by the controller or the processor pursuant article 37 GDPR. The primary role of the data protection officer (DPO) is to ensure that her organisation processes the personal data of its staff, customers, providers or any other individuals (also referred to as data subjects) in compliance with the applicable data protection rules.
Ethics Advisor	The ethics advisor is appointed by the consortium to advise and assist the consortium in understanding and appropriately addressing the ethics issues raised by their activities. The person, independent from the Consortium, will have to report independently to the Commission/Executive Agency, in addition to their role of advising the Consortium.
Generated data	Generated data are all those data that is collected, analyzed and produced during the duration of the project.
Metadata	Metadata is data about data. It contains information that makes it easier to find, use and manage data. For instance, HTML tags define layout for human readers. Semantic metadata helps computers to interpret data by adding references to concepts in a knowledge graph.
Open data	Data or content open for anyone to use, re-use or redistribute it, subjected at most to measures that preserve provenance and openness.
Personal data	Personal data is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual (natural person or 'data subject', pursuant to article 4 (1) GDPR)
Pseudonymization	The data from its direct identifiers will be divided so that linkage to a person is only possible with additional information that is held separately. The additional information must be kept separately and securely from processed data to ensure non-attribution. Pseudonymization still makes the data subject identifiable, through the combination of the pseudonym (e.g. key-code, code number) with additional identifiers. The time and the effort required to identify the individual as well as the available technologies are decisive for determining whether is possible to identify the data subject from pseudonymized data.
Re-used data	The re-used data are those pre-existing data that are already generated for other use, or those that the partners already have and/or for which they have to ask the access for.
Special categories of personal data	Pursuant to article 9 (1) GDPR: personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

Acronyms and abbreviations

Table 2: Acronyms and abbreviations

Terms	Definition
AI	Artificial intelligence
CB	Coordination Board
CWGs	Consultation and Working Groups
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
EU	European Union
EQY	Euroquality
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KC	Knowledge Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LLs	Living Labs
LRS	Azure Locally Redundant Storage
PID	Persistent Identifier
SES	Socio-Economic Status
SPG	Surveys, Protocols, Guidelines
TCA	True Cost Accounting
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) produced for the PLAN'EAT project is a dynamic document, which will be constantly updated. Subsequent versions of the document will be published by the Project Coordinator (CREA) at M24 (August 2024) and M48 (August 2025).

In this first version CREA has tried to outline the general objectives that must be followed by all PLAN'EAT partners in the management of data and metadata in accordance with the common FAIR data principles and GDPR. As specified in the document since this is the first version, clear guidelines on the methodology with which these principles should be applied, will be given to all partners as soon as possible.

The main topics of the DMP are shown as following:

- Description of the origin, type and utility outside the project of data generated and re-used in PLAN'EAT.
- Description of the process through which data management in the project will follow the FAIR principles, making the data generated in PLAN'EAT findable, accessible, interoperable and re-used.
- Addressing the general ethical aspect related to the data collected/generated in PLAN'EAT, specifying the principles that will be followed in the management of personal and special categories of personal data in accordance with the GDPR.
- Description of the strategy and tools used in the project to ensure a high level of data processing, data security, especially regarding personal and special categories of personal data.
- Description of other research output generated in PLAN'EAT.
- Providing an estimation of the resources that will be used during the project to allow the data generation according to FAIR principles.

1. Introduction

This document represents the Data Management Plan (DMP) of PLAN'EAT project, that receive funding from the European Union (EU) Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. To build up the document the European Commission (EC) template (1) for DMP was used, adapted to the context of the project. To harmonize the process, this document collects all the needs of the PLAN'EAT partners thanks to the use of the questionnaire answers provided by Work Package (WP) leaders, with the support of all the task partners. The respondents answers on data summary section allowed us to give an overview of the PLAN'EAT generated and re-use data, while for the other sections their contribution allowed us for set up the starting point for the data sharing, storing and processing and identifying gaps on which to organize the subsequent phases of the work.

The questionnaire is attached in the Annex 1.

This is the first version that collects the initial stage of data management of this project to ensure that the data collected all along the project will comply with the FAIR data principles. The document will be constantly updated during the project, and other two versions will be released at August 2024 (M24) and August 2026 (M48). CREA, as the coordinator, is the responsible for the DMP, and has its own DPO (responsabileprotezionedati@crea.gov.it).

Each partner will be responsible for the compliance with the legislation on the processing of personal data (GDPR UE Regulation 2016/679) and for the compliance with the rules on scientific research. All partners are responsible for their data generation. This DMP sets up the principles, methods and standards that should be applied to data processing process.

The understanding of the typology and amount of data that the project will generate made it clear the necessity to create an inter-disciplinary committee formed by experts on Open Data, personal data processing, development of DMP, ethical aspects, to which Ethical Advisor and each DPO partners should be part of.

Each partner, based on their contribution, is responsible for compliance with the mandatory legislation and the ethical principles that must guide the research.

1.1 Work Package descriptions

In the Table 3 the description of the project Work Package (WP) is provided.

Table 3: WP descriptions

	Description
WP1	<p>Snapshot of European dietary patterns and food environments:</p> <p>WP1 will start with an extensive literature review in the 11 EU Countries to assess the existing scientific basis on the transition towards healthy and sustainable dietary behaviour at local/national and European levels, to identify knowledge gaps to fill and best practices.</p> <p>Based on this state of the art, PLAN'EAT will map the dietary patterns for 9 pre-selected target population groups, analysing differences and peculiarities and identifying strengths and weaknesses. In parallel of dietary patterns mapping, WP1 partners will assess people's lived experiences of food environments to shed a light into how policies play out in practice and inform the design of more equitable and effective policies.</p>

WP2	<p>Understanding factors and drivers influencing dietary behaviour:</p> <p>WP2 will aim to identify, understand and influence mechanisms underlying dietary behaviours with high positive environmental, socio-economic and health impacts from the broader food environments and food systems in which these are embedded (macro, meso and micro-level). From this analysis, specific recommendations will be defined to modify behaviors with high impact potential. Of these 10 key leverage points from macro to micro-level will be selected for LL.</p>
WP3	<p>Understanding the environmental, social and health impacts of dietary choices:</p> <p>WP3 will aim to identify and understand the environmental, social and health impact of predominant dietary patterns highlighted in WP1 as relevant for different target groups. The true costs of the same dietary patterns will be measured, analysed and compared evaluating the positive and negative externalities thereof. Recommendations will be derived on dietary pattern transition.</p>
WP4	<p>Development of effective tools and strategies:</p> <p>Following the outcomes emerged in the previous WPs (in particular WP2 and WP3), WP4 will try to develop a series of coherent interventions in macro, meso and micro-level, which include methodologies, tools and materials, which can be used at European level both by policy makers and by actors in the food supply chain. The ultimate aim will be to try to steer a transition towards healthier and more sustainable dietary behaviour.</p>
WP5	<p>Living labs creation, implementation and consultation:</p> <p>WP5 will aim to manage the implementation of the LLs approach, from stakeholder gathering to solutions testing and replication planning. Effective methodologies and tools to create and run the 9 LLs will be designed and interaction with WP1-4 will be facilitated, notably to collect data, co-design interventions and test solutions.</p>
WP6	<p>Communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy:</p> <p>WP6 will aim to generate visibility (through social media, external events, etc..) and awareness for the project during the whole duration, to engage and empower stakeholders to build up on the outcomes and to apply best practices locally on the longer term. Dissemination will be ensured through the creation of a FAIR Knowledge Centre.</p>
WP7	<p>Project management:</p> <p>CREA with the collaboration of Euroquality (EQY) partner will ensure efficient coordination and data collection between partners, timely completion of all objectives, milestones and deliverables and proper reporting to the European Commission (EC).</p>

2. Data Summary

In this section, an overview of data generated and re-used in PLAN'EAT project will be given. First of all, the distinction between generated data and re-used data should be done. Generated data are all those data that is collected, analyzed and generated in the individual Work Packages. The re-used data are those pre-existing data that partners already have and/or for which they have to ask the access for.

2.1 Type of generated and re-used data

As shown in Table 4, the types of generated data were mainly those which come from questionnaire results, and statistical, modelling and analytical data. Instead, the re-used data are mainly those that come from the literature review. In both cases, the data format will be mainly as documents (word or excel files), images, videos and recordings. The size of the data will be variable, from documents that are sized less than 5MB to those database and tools (e.g., videos for the communications) that will weigh more than 10GB. However, due to the initial stage of the project, for some datasets there are still missing information.

Table 4: Type and characteristics of generated and re-used data

	Generated data	Re-used data
WP 1	Questionnaire data to assess the needs and the initiatives to encourage dietary behaviour changes and to improve food environments, modelling/statistical data to map the dietary pattern in the 9-target group of the Living Labs (LLs), photo, recording to map the food environment in the 9 LLs.	Questionnaire data from partners (snapshot of the 11 countries for food systems interventions), literature review to assess the existing scientific basis on the transition towards healthy and sustainable dietary behaviours, experts' interview from FAO and WHO, analytical data from international/national survey on dietary patterns.
WP 2	Expert interviews, workshops, focus groups, physiological parameters, survey and diary data from LL leaders, citizen panels, clinical samples, the Policy Lab and Consultation and Working Groups (CWGs).	Literature review, previous data collection from other projects (<i>physiological parameters</i>).
WP 3	Statistical and modeling data through the True Cost Accounting (TCA) database, modelling data on the environmental pressures and impact of diets, modelling data on the impact on animal welfare, use of antibiotics and labor requirement, analytical/modelling data to 'monetize' the environmental, social and health impacts of 3 selected European dietary patterns, literature data to realize the Data Gap Report that contains the translation of the impacts into true costs and the recommendations, qualitative data.	Statistical data from food balance sheets, modelling data for environmental and social impact assessment, literature data on socio-economic impacts, literature review for the environmental impacts of food, food composition and food sustainability databases.
WP 4	Participatory research (food policy summit), questionnaire data to test the effectiveness of policy actions and to design solutions for each food chain actor's needs, interviews, data from co-creation workshops for behavioural change interventions, randomized control trials and clinical studies on children/adolescents and adults with obesity and/or diabetes, decision trees and algorithms for personalised sustainable healthy eating recommendations, interviews from focus groups and workshops to have the consumer/user feedback on the application of the app for the personalized guidelines.	Quantitative and qualitative data generated by LLs, CWGs and WPs.
WP 5	Statistical and modelling data to support the creation of a measurement framework and the	Literature review of existing toolkits and previous EU projects, qualitative data of LLs

	monitoring activities in the LLs, questionnaire data from CWGs, questionnaire data from all Surveys, Protocols and Guidelines (SPGs) developed during the project.	insights and results to provide information for the local food system and stakeholders involved, statistical/analytical and modelling data generated by LLs and WPs.
WP 6	Press releases, Q&A, social media posts, articles for the press and other dissemination contents.	NA
WP7	Information on members of the consortium and stakeholders who will be contacted during the project.	NA

2.2 Origin of generated and re-used data

The generated data come from:

- Living Labs (LLs) surveys/research (especially those that will involve citizens panel);
- Consultation Working Groups (CWGs) members surveys/research;
- Interview with FAO/WHO.

The re-used data come from:

- Scientific literature;
- Food consumption and food composition database (from EFSA, EuroFIR, Nubel database);
- Food consumption national surveys;
- Food and agricultural data from various statistical sources, self-generated impact data using self-generated modelling methods;
- Governmental national reports/laws/regulations;
- Data collected in other projects;
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) databases;
- European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL).

2.3 The purpose and the utility outside the project of the generated and data re-use

The purpose of data generation and re-use together with the utility of data outside the project are shown in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5: The purpose of generated and re-used data

	What is the purpose of the data generation?	What is the purpose of the data re-use?
WP 1	Assessment of needs and current local/national/EU initiatives implemented to promote changing eating behaviours and improve food environments. Mapping of European dietary patterns of 9 different target groups from 9 European areas, analysing their differences and peculiarities, and of food environments across Europe.	Identifying factors and interventions influencing eating behaviour and assess the potential for dietary and lifestyle change in diets and lifestyles. Providing a current view of the drivers shaping food systems and the state of the art of existing policy interventions. Mapping European dietary patterns in the 11 countries that participate in the project.
WP 2	Identification of high impact behaviours, understanding of the behaviour determinants at micro-level and meso-	Similar as the generated data: delivering the project outputs, specifically to identify high

	level, understanding of macro-level factors influencing the food system, e.g. impact of food offer, food communication and food education, to feed into later project aim of developing interventions.	impact behaviours and existing knowledge regarding determinants.
WP 3	Delivering the project outputs such as the Data Gaps report, the Impact Map and the assessment of the true costs of three European diets. This includes an overview of the average true costs of 120+ foods consumed in the EU; understanding of the major environmental, social and health impacts of food consumption; overview of the data availability for true cost accounting assessments of European food consumption and identification of data gaps.	Same as the generated data: delivering the project outputs. This includes identifying and quantifying the food consumed in the EU, to identify relevant environmental, socio-economic and health impact of food production and consumption.
WP 4	Developing tools, policy recommendations, dietary guidelines, intervention strategies for behaviour change towards healthier and more sustainable food consumption in different settings (including in schools and with healthcare providers).	Same as the generated data.
WP 5	Defining a common methodology and the list of tools the LLs will use within the project activities to run a LL; defining a measurement framework and monitoring the impacts of the project's tools and interventions.	Defining a replication and a transfer roadmap; create the baseline scenario.
WP 6	Communicating the activities and the results of the project; building a strong and credible image of PLAN'EAT among external stakeholders and raising awareness of the issues addressed; generating interest of (potential) participants to plan PLAN'EAT activities at all levels.	NA
WP7	Contact of project members and external stakeholders.	NA

Table 6: Data utility outside the project

	To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project	
WP 1	Food chains actors, researchers/educational programmes, healthcare professionals, other project regarding food environments, policymakers.	
WP 2	Researchers, policymakers, healthcare professionals, consumers and further food chain actors.	
WP 3	Researchers, policymakers, private sector, NGOs, Think Tanks.	
WP 4	Local/national/European policymakers, consumers, schools and students, healthcare providers, farmers, researchers.	

WP 5	All organisations/projects that work with LLs; other research projects dealing with impacts on dietary behaviours of specific tools and interventions; policymakers to design data-driven policies; other territories that would adopt the PLAN'EAT LLs approach; who would like to reach or create other LLs.
WP 6	Stakeholders willing to disseminate the same type of information as the ones generated by the communication team of the PLAN'EAT project.
WP7	None

2.4 Personal data and special categories of personal data

In addition to this type of data, **personal and special categories of personal data will be collected. At this stage of the project, the partners have decided to collect the following data:**

- Personal data: Name, surname, zip code, emails, phone numbers, country of living or nationality, age, gender.
- Special categories of personal data: socio-economic status (SES), health status, educational level, household income, type of job, height, weight, eating behaviours (this kind of data could be considered as special categories of personal data when associated with data concerning health or food preferences (e.g. vegan, vegetarian pattern, etc...) pursuant to the article 9 (1) GDPR), someone answered 'maybe, don't know yet'.

3. FAIR Data

In this section, the procedure through which the data management will follow the FAIR principles is described.

Before listing the principles that will be followed in the PLAN'EAT project, an overview of the Open Science practices that the Consortium is going to implement will be given.

Open methodology

Whenever possible, the specific methodologies of the activities envisioned in PLAN'EAT will be described, discussed and shared openly outside of the Consortium. This will allow external experts panels (e.g. True Cost Accounting Community of Practice, European Network of Living Labs) to provide feedback, increasing awareness about the project. The design of the implementation strategies targeting citizens will be discussed directly with the concerned population group during user co-creation workshops. Implemented and assessed, the project's employed methodologies will be thoroughly documented and disclosed on the project's Knowledge Centre (KC).

Open Access to Research Outputs

The research outputs (e.g., data, new methodologies, new scientific knowledge) will be made accessible and shared throughout the duration of the project, except for the code used in the AI algorithms and recommended system web-based tool offering personalised dietary guidelines.

The raw data and results produced during the project will respect the FAIR principles and will be openly available on the PLAN'EAT Knowledge Centre after their anonymisation and providing that they will not compromise the privacy of participants. All data will be archived in a way that maximizes discoverability.

Scientific articles, conferences support and reports, and potential white papers will be open access to support future applied and fundamental research work as well as future policy recommendations, and thus maximize the project's impact.

Before opening access to the project's data, the Consortium will make sure that all relevant legislations are respected (e.g. GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the 27th of April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, etc.).

In the following sections, the principles of the FAIR data (2), that will be applied by the PLAN'EAT project, are presented, trying to comply with the request of the European Commission to provide open access to research data 'as open as possible as closed as necessary'.

In the FAIR principles, data and metadata will be taken into account. The term metadata refers to "structured information that describes, explains, locates, or otherwise makes it easier to retrieve, use, or manage an information resource. Metadata is often called data about data or information about information". To summarize, the metadata allows for a better comprehension and represent the way of description through which is possible to perform efficiently the research (the findability), the access (the accessibility) and the re-use (the reusable) of that data.

3.1 Making data findable, including provision for metadata

The first step to (re)use data consists of making them findable. The main principle to follow is that metadata and data should be easy findable by computers and humans. In order to achieve the findability, different tools should be identified.

3.1.1 PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER (PID)

A persistent identifier (PID) is something that identifies a document, file, web page, or other object (3,4). The most appropriate PIDs will be identified in order to make the data findable and understandable, and to help others to cite these data when reusing them. In particular, the PID to be used will be decided by PLAN'EAT data producers according to the typology of data/metadata, following specific guidelines in the decision process (e.g. DOI for digital outputs; ORCID for people,...)

Different PIDs will be used in order to identify different entities:

- Physical: e.g. people, instruments, artefacts, samples;
- Digital: e.g. documents, data, software, services - otherwise known as digital objects - and collections made of them;
- Conceptual: e.g. organisations, projects, vocabularies.

The characteristics that each PID has are the following:

- Unique: one PID per type of data (e.g. one specific DOI for each database; one specific ORCID for one person)
- Permanent: it remains valid in any cases (e.g. changing of the website for the product of the PID hosted);
- Linkable: the PID is linkable to its content.

3.1.2 METADATA STANDARD AND KEYWORDS

A metadata standard is a high-level document which establishes a common way of structuring and understanding data and includes principles and implementation issues for utilizing the standard. There are many metadata standards purposed for specific disciplines.

The common metadata standards (the protocols and standards used to structure the data) will be identified according to the typology of data and the choice of their repository. The metadata standards to apply will follow the RDA Metadata standard Catalog (Research Data Alliance) (5).

Keywords will be established to allow for potential re-use of data. The keywords will be identified when data will be uploaded on the repository and will be chosen to identify the different field of the project.

3.2 Making data accessible

Once findable, the users then need to have the access to the data and metadata. For this reason, when possible, the data sharing will respect the Open data principles, uploading the data and the metadata in the repository, with restrictions when necessary.

3.2.1 TRUSTED REPOSITORY

The data/metadata will be shared in a common trusted repository, such as Zenodo. The exact kind of repository will be identified with a clear overview of all type of data that will be collected. The decision will be approved by the Consortium of PLAN'EAT.

In addition to the trusted repository, EQY will develop by August 2023 (M12) a repository gathering all the data collected and generated during the project: dietary patterns and food environments mapping, dietary behaviour studies, impacts of food choices quantified and 'monetised' (TCA), etc.

The precise governance structure and business model for its further maintenance will be discussed within the exploitation strategy, ensuring the FAIR principles and GDPR compliance. The guidelines to deliver the repository will be given to partners for preparing their results to be integrated into the repository, including meta-data association.

3.2.2 DATA OPENLY AVAILABLE

Personal and special categories of personal data won't be shared in any form and for any reasons outside the PLAN'EAT project.

All partners will provide the data as openly as possible. However, some restrictions will be faced in some cases:

- License agreement conditions;
- Re-use of data that are not meant to be shared for other purposes than those established at the beginning of their use, at least in the raw form;
- Possible decision made up by ethics committee that will have to approve data collection and their use.

Since different partners, even though expressing the intention to openly share data, haven't had a clear idea yet, further information will be given in the DMP updated versions.

For the peer-review publication an embargo period is not permitted (publishing with an embargo period and on a journal that still offers this option do not represent an eligible cost). There aren't any other specifications for the embargo period for other type of publications.

3.2.3 ACCESS TO THE DATA: USING A STANDARDIZED PROTOCOL, RESTRICTIONS ON USE, AVAILABILITY AND FINDABILITY OF METADATA

Free and standardized access protocol to the data will be identified in later stages of the project, considering the availability, stability, and safety principles for the open data.

Restrictions on use, how the access will be provided, the identity of person accessing the data will be ascertained by CREA together with other partners. In particular, each task leader responsible for data handling will propose the best tools to achieve the access to data.

The access management will be established by the working group, including the possibility to identify a data access committee for personal and sensitive data.

How long the data project will be preserved together with the possibility to have the access to metadata when data are no longer available will be discussed with the partners in later stages of the project depending also on the cost of the maintenance.

The possible list of reference or document regarding any software that allow for the access, or the reading of the data will be included further after having discussed it together with the partners. This is because it is a step that will be clarified once the structure of the exact type of data generated will be available.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data are defined as interoperable when they are structured and described consistently, both syntactically and semantically, so different sources by both humans and machines can analyze and ensure that similar data is accurately compared with each other (6). The aim of the project will be to make data as interoperable as possible by creating a facilitated network of exchange and reuse of data inside and outside PLAN'EAT.

To achieve this aim, data collected/generated during our activities will be stored in an open file format (e.g. CSV, JSON, XML, etc..), deposited in a trusted repository and described using metadata standard (e.g. DDI – Data Documentation Initiative, Dublin Core Metadata, etc.) that will facilitate a comparison with different datasets from distinct sources.

Further information regarding the protocols used to facilitate this process will be provided in subsequent versions of DMP following consultation with PLAN'EAT partners.

3.3.1 VOCABULARY STANDARD

Datasets and all accompanying documents will be described through a standard and commonly used vocabulary based on the project's research domain, so that other scientists can make an assessment and reproduce the dataset. Among the standard vocabularies (7) we will try to choose vocabularies already used by other project with similar backgrounds in order to increase interoperability and reduce redundancies, thus encouraging data re-use.

3.3.2 LINK TO OTHER DATASET

Furthermore, it should be specified whether a dataset was built on another dataset outside or within the project or if complementary information is stored in a different dataset. This goal will be possible by creating as many meaningful links as possible to metadata resources. All datasets need to be properly cited (i.e., including their globally unique and PID).

3.4 Increase data re-use

Data shall be sufficiently annotated so that machine and human users can determine fitness for purpose in the context of their analysis.

3.4.1 LICENSE

The use of a license is necessary to correctly define the open data, ensuring the reusability of a dataset and building an equitable and accessible distribution of them, in line with the FAIR principles.

Peer-reviewed scientific publications in PLAN'EAT will be licensed under the latest version of a Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) (8). The less restrictive license is the international version 4, which gives recipients maximum freedom to do what they want with the work of the licensor.

Partners should provide information at least on: publication author(s), title, date of publication, place of publication, Horizon Europe funding, project name, acronym and concession number, license terms, persistent identifiers for publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and grant. Where applicable, the metadata shall include PIDs for any search results or any other tools necessary to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Third parties who reuse open data produced in PLAN'EAT must give credit to the original author(s) (=attribution) and indicate any changes, including a URL or link to the original work, this CC-BY license, and a copyright notice.

In subsequent versions of the DMP, further specifications will be provided regarding the individual cases of the data collected in PLAN'EAT where the dissemination of data will not be possible and for how long the data will remain available for third parties beyond the end of the project.

3.4.2 DOCUMENTATION

PLAN'EAT partners will provide additional documentation necessary to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use.

This documentation may include:

- Software,
- Algorithms,
- Protocols,
- Models,
- Workflows,
- Electronic notebooks,
- Codebooks,
- And others.

4. Ethics

4.1 General principles

In PLAN'EAT project, the compliance with the ethical principles and the applicable EU, international, and national laws for the ethics issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report and any additional ethics issues that may emerge in the course of the grant, will be ensured. For any applicable ethics issue, the guidance provided in the European Commission Ethics Self- Assessment Guidelines will be followed with the principles of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (10).

The ethics requirements that each partner has to follow are showed more in details in the Deliverable 7.4 (Ethics requirements).

Activities in the LLs. To perform the LLs activities, each LL must request the approval of its study from its local/national ethical committees. Local/national Ethical Committees will ensure the compliance of the studies involving human data collection with relevant regulations.

Participants will be recruited on a voluntary basis and after having expressed full informed consent, in the first year of the project and consulted all along its lifetime.

The LLs of PLAN'EAT will follow the rules and guidelines of the General Data Protection Regulation even in countries where the data protection laws may not be as strong following the procedure codified in this document.

Activities in the CWGs. The Consultation and Working Groups participations will include the informed consent with the same procedure that the LLs will follow. The ethical approval for the research that will be applied with the CWGs will not be necessary.

For all type of research and/or recruitment that involves the collection of personal and special categories of personal data, the informed consent will be signed up and stored according to the EU- CTR Regulation. Pursuant to the article 9 (2) (a), the consent will be collected after having provided the participants with all the information, pursuant to article 13 GDPR. The lawful base for data processing of special categories of personal data is the Article 9(2) (j) of the GDPR.

At this moment, it is not possible to establish if specific ethics or legal issue can have an impact on data sharing. Further information will be provided later on in the project when the data collection starts.

4.2 Handling of personal and human data

Personal data

The personal data will be collected during the participants recruitment process using a specific informed consent form that has the following characteristics: being free (voluntary and able to be withdrawn at any time), specific (referring to one or more identified purposes), informed (given in full awareness of all relevant consequences of giving consent).

A definition of informed consent will be adapted from EU- CTR Regulation relating to the implementation of good clinical practices in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use.

In addition to written data, audio and audio-visual recordings may be collected. The Consortium acknowledged that these constitute personal data and for this reason they will be handled as such in accordance with the provisions of the Regulation (UE) 2016/679 and EDPB Guidelines 05/2020 on consent.

A sheet to be signed will be given to the participants of the clinical/research studies. The first part regards the information sheet, that describes the purpose of the project, the main activities that participants will have to do, the advantages and disadvantages that the participants could face during the research, the handling of data/personal data and the possibility to withdraw from the research. The second part concerns the informed consent which includes the privacy aspects on the authorization to handle personal data.

The information sheet was realized in two versions: one for the LLs that will conduct clinical studies and another one for the LLs that will not conduct clinical studies but other typologies of research.

In case of the participation of children, that are unable to give informed consent, that is necessary for providing effective, the permission and informed consent will be obtained from legal representatives, teachers and school principals to conduct interviews/questionnaires with each child and to quote their speeches.

Humans data

Clinical studies involving human subjects will be conducted after the approval of the local ethics committee. When research will be conducted with children below 13 years old, the child's assent/dissent procedure will be conducted in addition: information about project activities will be adjusted to age groups and provided before and during the research. For those LLs which involve vulnerable individuals/groups, to minimize the risk of stigmatisation the activities will be conducted under the supervision of an experts in education and under the guidance of the Ethics Advisor.

The ethics risks related to the data processing activities must be evaluated. This evaluation must include an opinion if data protection impact assessment should be conducted under article 35 General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679. The risk evaluation and the opinion must be submitted as a deliverable before the start of the relevant activities.

5. Data Security

The aim of the PLAN'EAT project will be to securely store generated and re-used data in order to protect these from any loss or external manipulation.

5.1 SharePoint - Cloud

To increase the level of collaboration between partners within the project, the SharePoint cloud is used, hosted by Microsoft, as a safe place to store, organize, share and access information. This is where documents and data such as deliverables, reports, surveys, intermediate publication statuses, etc. are processed collaboratively.

External backups are not expected as a result of the SharePoint structure because it has a custom-built solution for storage of customer data in Azure Storage. Every file is simultaneously written into both a primary and a secondary data center region. After the contents are written into Azure Storage, checksums are stored separately with metadata, and are used to ensure that the committed write is identical to the original file sent to SharePoint during all future reads. Within each region, Azure Locally Redundant Storage (LRS) provides a high level of reliability (11).

No personal/sensitive data will be stored in this area, the only personal data present are those referring to the participants in the PLAN'EAT project (name, surname and email).

The SharePoint of the project is only accessible to authorized partners.

Later versions of the DMP will provide more information about the instructions supplied to partners so that personal data will not be shared in this Cloud.

5.2 Knowledge Centre – EQY Repository

EQY will develop the PLAN'EAT repository and deliver guidelines to partners for preparing their results to be integrated into the repository, including meta-data association. Aspects of data processing that concern EQY directly in the construction of this repository for the purposes of the project will be defined and contractually agreed pursuant to article 26 (or article.28) of GDPR, as mentioned in the Consortium Agreement 'In particular, the Parties shall, where necessary, conclude a separate data processing, data sharing and/or *joint controller agreement* before any data processing or data sharing takes place' (paragraph 4.4).

The first version of the Knowledge Centre will be accessible at M12. More information regarding data security will be provided in the second version of the DMP, after the building of KC.

5.3 Personal data and special categories of personal data

Special attention will be paid to data, documents, or other material (in any form) identified as sensitive in writing ("sensitive information") — throughout the duration of the project and if the partners request it the granting authority may agree to keep such information confidential for a longer period (GA p.32). Partners must process personal data in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/679) (GA p.35).

PLAN'EAT partners must ensure that personal data will be:

- Processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects;
- Collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;
- Adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- Accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
- Kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and - processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

5.3.1 DATA PROCESSING

As stated in recital 160 of Guidelines on consent (EDPB, 4 May 2020): Article 89 highlights the need for safeguards in data processing activities for scientific purposes. These purposes "*shall be subject to appropriate safeguards, in accordance with this regulation, for the rights and freedoms of data subject.*" Data minimization, pseudonymisation, anonymisation and data security are mentioned as possible safeguards.

Anonymisation is the preferred solution as soon as the purpose of the research can be achieved without the processing of personal data. If possible, partners will anonymise all personal data prior to its analysis and its release in the form of deliverables. These types of data will be stored on the local servers of the partners responsible for data collection, analysis and anonymization. Partners can grant access to personal and sensitive personal data only to those who have to process these data for the specific purposes of the project and following the drafting of a confidentiality obligation. Each person in charge of processing will be provided with credentials to access the systems to perform the tasks assigned to it.

For the qualitative data, the anonymisation involves the removal of all names, pseudonyms, specific occupational information, physical or electronic addresses, identification numbers, or other personal identifiers.

For the quantitative data, the anonymisation involves processing, analysing, and reporting results in aggregated form to ensure that specific participants cannot be identified.

For the special categories of personal data as age, physiological characteristics (e.g., height, weight), health status, SES and lifestyle will be collected and then will deploy decision trees and AI recommendation algorithms for the provision of personalized nutrition advice tailored to each user profile.

In some cases, for research purposes only, pseudonymization will be applied.

5.3.2 DATA STORAGE, RETENTION AND DESTRUCTION

An Ethical Advisor has been identified, and with his support together with that of the DPO, the Consortium will ensure that appropriate technical and organisational measures are taken to protect all personal data against accidental or unlawful disclosure, access, alteration, destruction, or loss. This will include the design of data collection instruments under the principle of privacy-by-design and -default, the storage of personal data in secure files on secure servers, and the storage of anonymised data and identifiers in separate secure files. In addition, the Consortium ensure strive to retain data for a period as short as possible relative to the type of research and the type of participant involved. The retention period of PLAN'EAT will coincide with the duration of the project being as long as it is necessary to fulfil the purposes of PLAN'EAT.

PLAN'EAT will focus on different profiles of vulnerable groups to better understand their concerns and mindsets so as to develop appropriate interventions. Information will be processed with special care (esp. health data) so that there will be the compliance with all regulations ensuring the trustworthiness between participants, avoiding stigmatisation.

6. Other research output

In addition to the generated and reused data outlined in this document, the PLAN'EAT project also will produce other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the project itself. These other research outputs consist of:

- Software for mapping the dietary pattern of the countries participating in PLAN'EAT project;
- Toolbox to set up a LL;
- New cereal-based foods;
- Web-based tool for personalized data;
- Food System Dashboard;
- Web-based tool for assessing the environmental sustainability of diets;
- Education intervention in schools on healthy and sustainable food behaviours;
- The project website

The project website will be managed by EQY and SOPEXA and will remain active for 5 years after the end of the project.

Since many other research outputs are still in progress at this initial stage of the project, our aim was to collect the majority of them in this first version of the DMP- with the possibility to add others to the list- and then discuss later on what will be the best strategy to manage them, at least for those outputs that will be generated in the first two years of the project. However, the FAIR principles will be applied where possible.

7. Allocation of resources

The Project Coordinator (CREA) is responsible for overall data management in PLAN'EAT project, including the elaboration of the DMP and its future updates (M24, M48). The PC, in collaboration with WP Leaders and Task Leaders, will decide when and how to share the data generated/collected in PLAN'EAT.

Long term preservation will be ensured by uploading the final data sets and publication to trusted repositories. During the project activities data will be stored in PC configured with appropriate security-aware settings at user level (e.g. installing security updates, anti-virus protection, local back-ups, blocking of certain software installation, etc.). Memory stick or other media easy to lose or access will not be used. Long term preservation will be carried out in secure cloud or hard disk. The allocation of resources for long term preservation will be discussed at a later stage of the project.

Conclusions and Next steps

This first version of PLAN'EAT DMP aimed to set up the initial guidelines to manage data and metadata that the project will produce (both using generated and re-used data), making them compatible with the FAIR principles. The DMP will be a document continuously updated.

The results that we collected in this survey from the partners helped us to understand which topics should be further explored with them. For this reason, specific meeting will be organized to take common decisions that will be approved by CREA together with the Coordination Board, and then with the Consortium. Workshops will be organized to share and explain to the partners the guidelines decided and the methods of implementation.

References

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10. ALLEA - All European Academies. The European Code of Conduct for research integrity. ISBN 978-3-00-055767-5. <https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/?cn-reloaded=1>
11. Introduction to SharePoint and OneDrive in Microsoft 365. <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/sharepoint/introduction>

Annex

Annex 1. The questionnaire

This questionnaire was filled in by the WP's leaders together with the collaboration of task's leaders. Not all questions were answered by the partners. What we collected from them helped us to understand the critical points to be further discussed.

DMP Questionnaire

Part 1. General information

1. Partners name (s):
2. For which Work Package (WP) are you the leader?
3. Please rate how important data management plan is for your work (1= less important; 10= highly important). Please highlight in yellow your answer.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

Part 2. Data summary

In this section, questions on generated data, meaning data that you will collect, analyze and generate in the individual work packages will be asked. Data that you already have or can get access over data repositories will be asked on another section of this questionnaire.

4. What types and formats of data will the project generate? (Types: e.g. modelling data, statistical data, analytical data, literature review, questionnaire data etc; Format: e.g. Image, Video, Audio, Presentations, Documents, etc...)

Answer

5. What is the purpose of the data generation and its relation to the objectives of the project? (e.g. answer to project outputs, share the data with local or international stakeholders, develop tools, etc...)

Answer

6. What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate? (<5MB; 5-20MB; 20-100MB; 100-500MB; 500-10GB; >10GB)

Answer

7. What is the origin/provenance of the generated data?

Answer

8. Will you collect sensitive personal data? (e.g. Personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, and data concerning health or sex life)

Yes

No

If Yes, can you describe what kind of data?

Answer

9. To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside PLAN'EAT project?

Answer

In this section you will be asked questions on re-use of data/existing data.

10. Will you re-use any existing data and for which reason will you re-use it?

Answer

11. What type and formats of data will the project re-use? (Types: e.g. modelling data, statistical data, analytical data, literature review, questionnaire data etc; Format: e.g. Image, Video, Audio, Presentations, Documents, etc...)

Answer

12. What is the purpose of the data re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project? (e.g. answer to project outputs, share the data with local or international stakeholders, develop tools, etc...)

Answer

13. What is the expected size of the datasets that you intend to re-use? (<5MB; 5-20MB; 20-100MB; 100-500MB; 500-10GB; >10GB)

Answer

14. What is the origin/provenance of the re-used data?

Answer

15. Will you collect sensitive personal data (e.g. Personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade-union membership, and data concerning health or sex life)

Yes

No

If Yes, can you describe what kind of data?

Answer

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Answer

Part 3 FAIR data

"In 2016, the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship' were published in Scientific Data. The authors intended to provide guidelines to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. The principles emphasise machine-actionability (i.e., the capacity of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume, complexity, and creation speed of data." (Online web-site: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/> ; Article: <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>).

16. Do you apply the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets) in your research?

Yes

Partially

No

Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata:

17. Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Yes

No

I don't know yet

18. What metadata will be created and what general standards will be followed (please provide a short description of the metadata standards)? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Answer

19. Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the potential re-use?

- Yes
 No
 I don't know yet

Making data Accessible:

20. Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

- Yes
 No

If yes, in which one?

21. Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

- Yes
 No
 Not yet

22. Will all data be made openly available? (If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement)

- Yes
 No
 Other answer

23. Will your data and publication need an embargo period?

- Yes
 No
 Maybe

24. Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

- Yes
 No

I don't know yet

If yes, could you give us a brief description of the access protocol?

Answer

25. If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

Answer

26. How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Answer

27. Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Answer

28. How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Answer

29. Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Answer

Making data Interoperable:

30. What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

Answer

31. Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Yes

No

I don't know yet

If yes, could you give us a brief description?

Increase data Re-use

32. How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Answer

33. Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

Answer

34. Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

- No
- I don't know yet

35. Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know yet

Part 4 Data security

36. What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Answer

37. Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know yet

If yes, in which way?

Part 5 Ethics

38. Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know yet

If yes, please provide a description of the possible ethics or legal issues

Answer

39. Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know yet

Part 6 Other research outputs

40. In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Answer (please you could give a short description or say if it's not applicable)

41. Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

Answer (please you could give a short description or say if it's not applicable)

Part 7 Allocation for resources

42. What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

Answer

43. How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Answer

44. Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Answer

45. How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (e.g. costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Answer

Part 8 Additional aspects that were not asked but that you think they are necessary to add

Answer